

Finding the Value of Any Number Raised to Power 0

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Abstract:- All humans are based on mathematical formula that's why one medicine applied to one difficult puzzle solves it.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this we are trying to define the yet unknown any number raised to power zero.

Ease of use

Here, I have calculated it for two numbers .I don't know what you have considered in log tables.

I think my proposition is correct.

a is any number where g,m,n are also numbers

formula $g^m \times g^n = g^{m+n}$

$$a^0 = a^{0+0+0}$$

$$(a^0).(a^0).(a^0) = a^{0+0+0}$$

$$(a^0)^3 = a^0$$

It is not 1 how can number generate same value for different powers here they are 3 and 1. It can only be true for $a^0=1$

It can never be true for any other number

It can be calculated cause for each number it will give a different value.

Example1

$$10^0 = x$$

Integrate both sides, we get

$$10^{0+1} = x^2/2$$

$$20 = x^2$$

$$x = 2 \text{ root } 5$$

Example2

$$2^0 = y$$

Integrate

$$2 = y^2/2$$

$$4 = y^2$$

$$2 = y$$

II. CONCLUSION

One number raised to a power always gives different result when it is raised to another power. So why 0 be different .it also gives different result each time.

REFERENCES

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- [5.] NCERT BOOKS of classes 6 to 12
- [6.] I studied them by heart they are knowledge Which is the curriculum of Central board of secondary education in Delhi and other parts of India.